

HOME SECURITY SYSTEM USING RTD SENSORS

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Abstract

Nowadays Home security is the most concerning problems as homes and even offices need to be secure from theft, leak in raw gas and fire. A wireless sensor network-based network coupled with GSM technology will be able to solve the problem to some extent. Recent advances in the field of Information Technology have made Information Security an inseparable aspect of the networks. Authentication plays an important role in security domain. With the advent of internet of things and efficient communication technologies, there has been an increasing trend for home automation. In this paper we have tried to explain various security issues in existing systems of security and implemented a new and trending technology based on network of RTD sensors to secure our homes and homely goods. Use of RTD sensors, which detect the body temperature of trespassers and alarm the inhabitant about the possible security threats. RTD based sensor model is more efficient and robust than the recent state of art models.

Keywords: - Sensor, GSM, Security, Intrusion, RTD Sensor, CCTV.

1. INTRODUCTION

A significant technological revolution is being sparked by the convergence of home automation and the internet of things. Home automation is being pushed forward by the internet of things in our daily lives [1]. IoT refers to a network of physical systems, vehicles, computing devices, mechanical, and digital machines that are connected to the internet and equipped with sensors, software, and network connectivity [2] Using processors and microcontrollers, these sensors sense information, gather it, and transmit it to the internet. Businesses across a range of industries are utilizing IoT to run more effectively, better understand their customers to provide more intensive customer service, enhance decision-making, and ultimately boost the value of the company. By Security, it is conceived a state of danger free and risk-free state of affairs. In other words, Security is the degree of resistance to, or protection from, harm. Vulnerable and valuable assets such as a person, dwelling, community nation, or organization have security concerns which are needed to be redressed. Security and safety are the two topics which every person is familiar to, as well as concerned with [3]. Every Industry, every home and every office need to be secure and safe. The safety of the possessions is of main concern to everyone, be it the safety of property or the safety and security of our loved ones.

2. PERCEIVED SECURITY VS. REAL SECURITY

It is worthy to mention here that there is a lot of difference between the perceived and Real Security. The notion of perceived and real security can be better understood by comparing the no of causalities are caused by an earth

quake or persons falling on the bathroom floor. Interestingly the no of deaths caused by later are far greater than the former [4]. Mapping this notion in case computer systems it can be conceived that if two computer security programs are interfering with each other and cancelling each other's effect, we view it as if our security is being doubled which in actual is not the case. Théâtre is a critical term for deployment of measures primarily aimed at raising subjective security without a genuine or commensurate concern for the effects of that measure on objective security [5]. For example, some consider the screening of airline passengers based on static databases to have been Security Theatre and Computer Assisted Passenger Pre-screening System to have created a decrease in objective security. Security perception leads to enhanced objectivity when it counteracts malicious behavior. By saying so it is meant that in case of security protections such as Alarm systems, surveillance systems, Anti-theft vehicle systems, the interloper, invader or a violator is usually discouraged to break into such systems. Hence there is less chance of external damage in addition to the internal security of the system. Physical security can be ensured by measures that do not allow unauthorized access to systems, equipment and resources. It is pertinent to mention here that there are multiple layers of physical security which are interdependent and collaboration of these layers provides full proof security. These layers consist of CCTV surveillance, security guards, protective barriers, access control protocols many more modern techniques.

Physical security measures are intended to perform following important functions

- Preempt potential intruders involving use of warning signs and perimeter markings.
- Differentiate between authorized and unauthorized accesses using keys, badges etc.
- Employing techniques that delay, frustrate and ideally prevent potential intruder by employing strong walls, door locks and safes.
- Intrusion detection by the use of intruder alarms and CCTV.
- Triggering of instant responses by security personal.

Beginning with home security

Home security has been the concern of the masses from time immemorial and it has been one of the most discussed topics. Home security requires a powerful security system which will secure it from theft, crime, fire, intrusion in addition to potential violations and infringement of home security. Conventional security systems use cameras and process large amounts of data to extract features with high cost and hence require significant infrastructures. This paper proposes a PIR sensor based low-cost security system for home applications in which Passive Infrared (PIR) sensor has been implemented to sense the motion of human through the detection of infrared radiated from that human body [6]. PIR device does not emit an infrared beam but passively accepts incoming infrared radiation. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of the system. PIR sensor detects the presence of human in the home and generates pulse which is read by the microcontroller. According to the pulse received by microcontroller, a call is established to mobile station through a GSM modem and thus warns the presence of human in the home to owner-occupier. On the other hand, this security system remains in idle position and performs nothing if no one is in the home.

Related works

Today's indoor security systems built with various sensors such as ultrasonic detectors, microwave detectors, photoelectric detectors, infrared detectors etc. Each of these systems has its own limitations. As an example, photo-electric beam systems detect the presence of an intruder by transmitting visible or infrared light beams across an area, where these beams maybe obstructed. But the drawback lies within it if the intruder is aware of the presence of this system. Despite of having strong dependence on surrounding environmental status, pyroelectricity has become a widely used detection parameter because of simplicity and privilege of interfacing to the digital systems [7]. Now, it is extensively used for intruder detection, smart environment sensing, and power management applications. Several works have been conducted in various applications. Intelligent fireproof and theft-proof alarm system, GSM (Global System for Mobile) network-based home safeguard system, human tracking system and intruder detection systems are some notable works done previously based on pyroelectricity sensing technique. Our work introduces a low-cost security system solution. Utilization of existing cellular network to alert and inform the system

owner about the security breach is made to cope up with ever-increasing demand for cheap but reliable security system.

PIR sensor

PIR is basically made of Pyroelectric sensors to develop an electric signal in response to a change in the incident thermal radiation. Every living body emits some low-level radiations and the hotter the body, the more is emitted radiation. Commercial PIR sensors typically include two IR-sensitive elements with opposite polarization housed in a hermetically sealed metal with a window made of IR-transmissive material (typically coated silicon to protect the sensing element). When the sensor is idle, both slots detect the same amount of IR, the ambient amount radiated from the room or walls or outdoors [8]. When a warm body like a human or an animal pass by, it first intercepts one half of the PIR sensor which causes a positive differential change between the two halves. When the warm body leaves the sensing area, the reverse happens, whereby the sensor generates a negative differential change. These change pulses are what is detected. In order to shape the FOV, i.e., Field of View of the sensor, the detector is equipped with lenses in front of it. The lens used here is inexpensive and lightweight plastic materials with transmission characteristics suited for the desired wavelength range. To cover much larger area, detection lens is split up into multiple sections, each section of which is a Fresnel lens. Fresnel lens condenses light. Providing a larger range of IR to the sensor it can span over several tens of degree width [9]. Thus, total configuration improves immunity to changes in background temperature, noise or humidity and causes a shorter settling time of the output after a body moved in or out the FOV [10]. Along with pyroelectric sensor, a chip named Micro Power PIR Motion Detector IC has been used. This chip takes the output of the sensor and does some minor processing on it to emit a digital output pulse from the analog sensor. Schematic of PIR sensor output waveform is shown in Fig. For triggering purpose, there are three dedicated pins in the PIR module: HIGH, LOW and COMMON. When connecting up LOW and COMMON pins, the output turns on and off every second or so when moving in front of it. That is called "non-retriggering" and shown in Fig. 1. When connecting up HIGH and COMMON pins, the output stay on the entire time that something is moving. That is called "retriggering"

Figure 1 Home security system using sensors

3. SECURITY WITH RTD SENSORS

One of the most important aspects of the sensor technology is the diversity of its applications which can range from very basic to very complex ones. In this abstract I am trying to utilize same for the same security

systems or keeping a house under surveillance. The basic idea is to utilize the sensor tech to make an alarm go off if some wrong is about to happen around [11]. The idea is to set a perimeter using this tech. The sensors used for this application can be wired or wireless ones (both having their pros and cons wired being simple to implement but prone to faults while the case with wireless is harder to implement but a bit more reliable). The key feature of the tech will be its capability to distinguish between the real alarm in case of burglary and the false alarm caused by some equipment malfunction or any other reason [12]. The idea is simple to mount the walls of the property with sensors (wireless or wired) and thus setting up a perimeter, if any one tries to jump over or cross the perimeter the alarm will buzz off and thus providing the owner with the facility to adjust to the robbery, burglary or even the assault each of the walls surrounding the property will have sensors based on the range to be covered (for wireless we can use infrared, Microwave sensor tech which will have a transmitter and receiver pair for every wall and for wired we can have wire guidance sensor, RTD sensors (wired wound sensors)[12].

The advantages of these sensors in addition to safeguarding from the home or property theft is to provide the victim with the additional time to make some emergency moves like calling police, relation, neighbor etc.

Figure 2 Implementation of Home security system

Here is a further information about the kind of sensors used in our technology.

4. WHAT IS AN RTD?

Temperature sensors also called Resistance Temperature Detectors (RTDs) include a resistor which changes resistance value in response to temperature. They have gained a reputation for accuracy, reproducibility, and stability [13] and have been used for many years to detect temperature in laboratory and industrial applications. As opposed to a thermocouple or thermistor sensor we use RTDs. Each sort of temperature sensor is best used under a specific set of circumstances that have a number of benefits such as:

- A large temperature range (-200 to 850°C for wire-wound and -50 to 500°C for thin film).
- Superior precision to thermocouples; excellent interchangeability
- Consistency across time

RTDs can be employed in all but the highest-temperature industrial processes because of their temperature range of 850°C. They are exceedingly stable and unaffected by corrosion or oxidation when created utilizing metals like

platinum. RTDs have also been made from other materials, including nickel, copper, and nickel-iron alloy. However, due to their lesser temperature capabilities and weaker stability and repeatability than platinum, these materials are not frequently employed.

Figure 3 Various types of RTD sensors

5. CONCLUSION

In its most basic form, home automation is the ability to control lighting, household, and image reorganization appliances remotely. By combining wireless sensor networks and GSM technology, this proposes a new solution for remote home security and device control system. Safety from theft, leaks of raw gas, and fire are also among the most important requirements of homes for people. The system is made up of a mobile phone, a data collection node, a device control node, and an ARM7-based WSN centre node with a GSM module. The PIR, temperature, smoke, and gas sensors are each attached to a separate WSN data collecting node module, and they all feed data to the data collecting node. Information Security is now an integral component of information technology thanks to advancements in that field.

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